

SHORT NOTES

Determination of Molecular Weights and Characterisation of 1-Hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazoles

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The preparation of a few substituted 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazoles has already been reported¹. Determination of their molecular weight by commonly used methods (including Rast's method) provided erratic results. During the present investigation, two methods have been developed for finding out their molecular weights. One depends on their property of forming salts with aniline in beautiful crystalline forms. After the estimation of aniline in a known quantity of the aniline salt of a hydroxybenzotriazole by titration against bromate and bromide mixture, the molecular weight of the triazole is calculated. The second method takes advantage of the insolubility of silver salts of hydroxybenzotriazoles in water. A known amount of the silver salt of a hydroxybenzotriazole is decomposed by hydrochloric acid and the silver chloride formed is weighed after washing it with water and ethanol, followed by drying. Knowing the amount of silver in weighed quantity of silver salt of the triazole, its molecular weight is calculated. The method used in the determination of the equivalent weight of an acid by pyrolysis of its silver salt could not be used in the case of silver salts of triazoles as these explode on heating.

As the aniline derivatives are solids which crystallise well and invariably melt at lower temperatures than the parent compounds, these are recommended for the characterisation of hydroxybenzotriazoles.

Salts of 1-Hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazoles with Aniline.—Equimolecular proportions of a substituted 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole and aniline, dissolved in ethanol, were heated for 10 to 15 minutes on a water bath. On cooling, the crystals of the salt separating were purified from benzene.

Following the procedure, the aniline salts of a few 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazoles were prepared (Table I).

Silver Salts of 1-Hydroxy-1, 2, 3-benzotriazoles.—To the silver nitrate solution was added a solution of a 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole in ethanol. The resulting solid separating was washed with water and dried at 80-85°.

1. Joshi and Deorha, *this Journal*, 1952, 29, 545; 1960, 37, 690.

Determination of Molecular Weights: (i) Aniline Salt Method.—To a known amount of the aniline salt (about 0.2 g.) of a 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole, suspended in water (20 ml), HCl (conc., 10 ml) was added. The amount of aniline was estimated by titrating against bromate-bromide solution in the usual way².

(ii) Silver Salt Method.—A known amount (about 0.3 g.) of the silver salt of a hydroxybenzotriazole was warmed with 5*N*-HCl at about 60°. After an hour on cooling, the mixture was filtered in a sintered crucible. The precipitate after being washed well with water till free of Cl⁻ ions and then with ethanol to remove any 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole was dried to a constant weight at 100-10°.

TABLE I

1-Hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazole.	Aniline salts.			%Nitrogen.		Colour of Ag salt.	M. W. of triazole.		
	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found	Reqd.		Silver salt.	Aniline salt.	Calc.
6-Chloro-	165°	C	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ON ₃ Cl	21.12	21.33	C	168.0	169.1	169.5
6-Bromo-	168°	C	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ON ₃ Br	18.51	18.24	C	214.4	213.1	214.0
4-Chloro-6-nitro-	170°	Cy	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	22.50	22.76	Y	213.9	214.1	214.5
4-Bromo-6-nitro-	175°	Cy	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Br	19.73	19.88	Y	257.9	258.2	259.0
6-Chloro-4-nitro-	185°	R	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	22.87	22.76	Fr	213.2	213.9	214.5
6-Bromo-4-nitro-	187°	R	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Br	19.68	19.88	Fr	258.4	259.3	259.0
6-Nitro-5-methyl-	159°	Y	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	24.14	24.39	Y	193.8	194.2	194.1
4,6-Dinitro-7-methyl-	184°	OY	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₆	25.54	25.30	OY	238.8	238.6	239.1
4-Bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl-	194°	Y	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ Br	19.08	19.12	Y	272.5	272.8	273.0
4-Chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-	190°	Y	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	21.49	21.77	Y	226.9	227.8	228.5
6-Bromo-4-nitro-7-methyl-	178°	Y	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ Br	19.33	19.12	Y	272.3	273.4	271.0
6-Chloro-4-nitro-7-methyl-	156°	OY	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	21.49	21.77	Y	227.1	228.2	228.5
6-Nitro-4-methyl-	180°	OY	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	24.19	24.39	Y	194.3	193.8	194.1

N.B. C=colourless, Y=yellow, OY=Orange-yellow, Fr=Scarlet-red, Cy=Cream yellow, R=red.

Molecular weights of 1-hydroxy-1,2,3-benzotriazoles, determined by the above methods, are recorded in Table I.

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